

Challenges and Opportunities of E-banking: in the case of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia in Dukem Area

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We collected and analyzed the data through self-sponsored. Cross bonding regarding this article should be addressed to Biruk Tessema PhD Candidate, Faculty of Management, Parul University, Gujarat, India

Abstract

The research aims to examine the difficulties faced by ATM and POS banking at the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia in the Dukem Area. It gathered data from bank staff and customers through questionnaires and interviews. The study highlighted the advantages of e-banking services for customers and the bank, as well as the significant challenges for ATM and POS services, such as the absence of a suitable legal and regulatory framework for e-commerce and e-payment in Ethiopia. The study proposes several measures for the government and the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia to address the identified challenges.

Key words: E-banking, ATM, POS, Information Technology, Challenges and opportunities

Introduction

Background of the Study

Nowadays modern technology is being introduced in all fields and it is changing the world with full of innovations. In this regard, information technology is considered as the key driver for the changes to take place around the world. For this reason, the traditional banking services are getting modernized by the use of electronic banking. These changes are made mainly due to the developments in information and communication technology. Due to this growth in information and communication technology, the banking industry is entering into new phenomena of unprecedented form of competition supported by modern information and communication infrastructure especially through the use of internet (Michael, 2013).

Creating an electronic banking in Ethiopia is the same as to building a web business for all who are participating in the economy of the country. Among electronic banking (E-banking) ATM, POS machine, Internet and Mobile banking a few which are used in CBE. This leads the country to the electronic business (e-business). The E- business, E-commerce is about using electronic techniques to create opportunities, create new markets, new processes and growth the creation of wealth using electronic mediums (Million, 2013).

ATM is commonly used by customers of various banks for cash withdrawal and account balance enquiry, water and electricity, fund transfer. A customer can access an ATM and POS machine by using an ATM card. An ATM card is a plastic card that allows the bank account holder to do the same things at an ATM as he or she would do at a bank also referred to ATM as a type of innovation that can mechanically accept issue withdrawals, transfer funds between accounts, collect bills and make small

loans. A well-functioning ATM is a sure way of improving service quality in the banking industry (CBE, 2023).

But the implementation of E-banking system is not likely to be considered successful if users are unmotivated to use that type of technology, and thus it will not bring full benefits to the organization. In order to motivate customers to use electronic banking, banks must make key improvements that address the customers' concerns. Although electronic banking introduces many benefits for banks and customers; customers still fear from the risk of electronic banking services (Mohammad, 2012).

Hence, in order to help banks improve e-banking adoption in general and ATM banking in particular by their customers, it is necessary to investigate the challenges and opportunities of ATM and POS Banking in Case of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia Dukem area.

Electronic banking is a driving force that is changing the banking industry towards a more competitive and efficient situation. The main driver behind electronic banking is convenience. It is available around the clock, is extremely time-saving, and is accessible from anywhere around the world. Electronic banking is very efficient, and has helped cut down a lot of costs, and in the case of virtual banks it has cut down almost all costs (Michael, 2013).

With all these benefits and opportunities that electronic banking offers to the Ethiopian banking industry, there are a number of challenges which commercial banks operating in the country are facing in the provision of electronic banking services in generally and in study area specifically. In addition to the above-mentioned challenges some of the customers may not collect their personalized cards and PINs from branches even if they are informed.

Keeping personalized cards and PINs for longer time is a risk for the branch and the bank.

Thus, in event of customer's failure to collect their cards and PINs for more than 3 months after the branch receives the cards; the branch shall destroy the cards using the banks procedures (CBE, 2023).

Electronic banking presents both an opportunity and a challenge in terms of being able to provide the convenience, efficiency, and effectiveness of electronic banking to its customers (Michael, 2013).

One of the major hindrances of ATM and POS machine is lack of appropriate technological infrastructure to support the service in study area. So, the researcher interested to identify

challenges and opportunities of ATM and POS banking in case of study area and try to give solid recommendation for the identified problems.

Review of Related Literatures

Electronic banking (E-banking)

Electronic banking (E-banking) is the means by which the services and products of banks are made available to their customers through the use of internet and electronic digital devices irrespective of the location of the customer and time of carrying out the transaction (Ovia, 2002). E-banking is the provision of banking products and services to banks and customers through the utilization of various electronic delivery channels. The e-banking concept has been in existence for some time although in form of Automated Tellers Machines (ATMs) and telephone banking and that in most recent times due to advancement in IT, it has been carried out through the use of the internet (Ovia, 2002).

The internet offers around the clock services irrespective of the customer's location, which gives customers the opportunity with ease and convenience to perform banking transactions such as cash withdrawals, money transfer, payments for goods and services, payment of utility bills, and so on, at any hour of the day Chavan (2013). E-banking is the automated delivery of banking services and products to customers through the use of electronic interactive communication channels. This definition implies that e-banking platforms or channels enable bank customers to perform banking transactions such as funds transfer, cash withdrawals, payment for goods and services, etc through the use of interactive electronic media that allow the customers to carry out transactions by themselves without relying on bank Tellers (Elisha, 2010).

Role of ICT in E-Banking

Information and communication technologies are playing a very important role in the advancements in banking. In fact information and communication technologies (ICT) are enabling banks to make radical changes to the way they operate. According to Consoli (2003), the historical paradigm of IT provides useful insights that opened the way to radical changes in

the banking industry such as the reconfiguration of its organizational structure and the diversification of the product line. Banks are essentially intermediaries, which create added value by storing, manipulating and transferring purchasing power between different parties. To achieve this, banks rely on ICT to perform most functions, from book keeping to information storage and from enabling cash withdrawals to communicating with customers (Shah et al., 2009).

In developed countries at least, this high degree of reliance on ICT means that banks spend a large chunk of their budget on acquiring as well as maintaining these technologies. Information Communication Technology provides a very limited return unless accompanied by changes in organizational structures and business processes. These changes also need to be followed by a diversification of service offerings, with many banks introducing new product lines such as credit cards, stock brokerage and investment management services. Thus, ICT has mostly enhanced productivity, as well as increased the choice for customers both in terms of variety of services available and in terms of the ways in which they are able to conduct their financial activities (Shah et al., 2009).

The Various E-banking channels

1. Telephone Banking

Telephone banking (also known as Tele-Banking) is an e-banking service provided by commercial bank for utilization by customers. The telephone banking channel enables customers to carry out banking transactions such as confirmation of account balance and confirmation of other banking information over the telephone (Edemivwaye, 2015).

2. Mobile Banking

Mobile banking (also known as M-banking) is an e-banking platform that allows customers to carry out banking transactions and make enquiries through the use of a digital mobile phone that is connected to a telecommunication network or wireless network. The earliest mobile banking services were offered through sending and receiving Short Message Service (SMS) (Shah et al., 2009).

3. Online Banking

Online banking (also known as Internet banking) provides a platform for bank customers to carry out financial transactions on their own through the use of a secured internet website operated by the commercial bank, a retail or virtual bank, credit union or building society (Edojariogba, 2014). The internet banking enables customers to access their financial institutions' online banking facility with access details, access codes, and passwords given to them by the financial institutions (Edojariogba, 2014).

4. Point-of-Sale (POS)

The POS e-banking channel allows customers to make payment for goods and services to clients. A Point Of Sale terminal is a portable device that allows customers with cards (such as ATM cards) to carry out banking transactions outside the banks environment. This ebanking platform allows bank customers to carry out financial transactions with clients (merchants) who have the device deployed in their premises irrespective of the merchant's bank and the customers bank (Okechi et al., 2013). The POS services enable customers transacting with merchants to make cashless payments for goods and services directly into the merchants account (Edemivwaye 2015).

5. Automated Tellers Machines (ATMs)

An Automated Tellers Machine (ATM) is an electronic banking outlet, which allows customers to complete basic transactions without the aid of a branch representative or tellers. Anyone with a credit card or debit card can access most ATMs. ATM is a computerized telecommunications device that provides the clients of a financial institution with access to financial transactions in a public space without the need for a cashier, human clerk or bank tellers. ATM transaction typically involves withdrawing cash from a machine. The consumer presents an ATM card, which is issued by the bank holding his or her checking account, at an ATM terminal, which may or may not be owned by the same bank. The consumer enters a personal identification number (PIN) to verify identity, once the PIN is verified, one can easily get the service, such as to withdraw cash, obtain bank statements, effect cash transfers, as he got from cashier or bank tellers (Fumiko, etal).

ATM Industry pricing

A guide to ATM and Debit Card Industry divided ATM Industry pricing in to two. ATM Industry pricing are retail fees paid by consumers and wholesale fees, which are exchanged between various members of the ATM infrastructure. The aforementioned components are explained as follows: *Retail ATM fees* Retail fees paid by ATM cardholders go to the cardholder's bank. Some fees are periodic, while others are assessed on a per-transaction basis. Among the former, the bank may charge an annual fee to depositors who choose to use ATM services or a card fee each time an ATM card is issued. Among the latter, the bank may charge a foreign fee when the cardholder uses an ATM not owned by the bank or an on-up fee when the cardholder uses an ATM owned by the bank. A surcharge is a retail ATM fee that is paid to the owner of the ATM, typically only when the cardholder uses an ATM not owned by the cardholder's bank. The level of a surcharge is set by the ATM owner: *Wholesale ATM fees* Wholesale ATM fees are set by networks. Periodic fees are paid to the network and include membership fees that are paid when a bank joins a network as well as monthly or annual fees that are tied to the sales volume of the bank's card program (D.W. and Alan, 1998).

ATM Transactions

ATM follows four transactions methods. These are Native transactions, Network on-us transactions, Reciprocal transactions and National bridge transactions. Each of them is: *Native transactions*: are not routed through any network switch. In the simplest case, which is called an "owner's on-us" transaction, a cardholder uses an ATM owned by his or her bank. Because the entire transaction is routed only through the issuing bank's systems, there is no need to involve a network switch. A variation is where the cardholder uses an ATM that does not belong to his or her bank but the card issuing bank and the ATM owner use the same processor. Some networks allow the processor to route transactions among its clients without involving the network switch, even when the ATM owner and the card issuer of the transaction are different institutions. Such transactions are called "processor's on-us" transactions. *Network on-us*: transactions are routed through only one network switch (David, 1999).

The switch can be either a regional network's or a national network's. Typically a network on-us transaction is initiated by a cardholder of one member institution at an ATM of another member institution. *Reciprocal transaction*: occur when the cardholder uses an ATM of another institution and the card issuer and ATM owners use different regional networks but the networks have a reciprocal-sharing agreement. A reciprocity agreement between regional networks is an arrangement whereby the two networks agree to pass information to one another in transactions involving members of each network. Typically, two network switches are necessary to complete the transaction: *National bridge transactions*: occur when the cardholder uses an ATM of another institution and the card issuer and ATM owners use different regional networks but the networks do not have a reciprocal sharing agreement. In this case the card issuer and ATM owner must belong to the same national network (Cirrus or Plus) and the regional networks serve as gateways to the national network. The transaction involves three switches, one from the initiating regional network, one from the national network, and one from the other regional network (David, 1999)

Electronic Banking in Developing Nations

Most of Ethiopian banks have adopted new and innovative ways to improve service delivery in a bid to combat competition. One significant means of achieving competitive advantage has been the adoption of e-banking services. The earliest forms of ICT technology employed by Ethiopian banks were mainly office automation devices such as telephones, telex and the facsimile. For many years these remained the main technologies utilized in transacting bank business (Abor, 2004), until later in the 1980s when the personal computer (PC) gained popularity.

Arguably, the most revolutionary electronic banking innovation in this country and the world over has been the Automated Teller Machine (ATM) and the numerous electronic cards. Currently, in addition to ATMs, most of the banks have implemented internet banking, telephone banking, and SMS alerts among others to deploy banking services to the customers. Anecdotal evidence however, indicates that the adoption of these electronic services is below expectation in Ethiopia thereby calling for a need to investigate the challenges affecting customer adoption of e-banking services. Even if there is a large amount of studies investigating

the challenges of adopting e-banking services globally and in the African context, a closer search through the literature indicates that prior studies have investigated more intensively on the economic return aspects rather than the challenges and opportunities that derive from the e-banking service rendering. This study aims at providing a broader conceptual insight and lays a framework for investigating challenges banks face in effectively implementing e-banking services in developing a developing country such as Ethiopia. The study uses qualitative method that seems more indicated to dissect and analyze the institutional based challenges as well as user- based challenges and opportunities that affect the e-banking products in Ethiopia related to the CBE (Sherif, 2006).

E-Banking in the African and Ethiopian Context

In the Ethiopian context, most if not all banks are making greater use of e-banking facilities to provide better services in order to excel in the competitive and ever growing banking sector. The spread of e-banking has greatly benefited the ordinary customer in general and the corporate world in particular. Consequently, electronic banking has been a priority on the agenda of many Ethiopian banks. These banks have been increasingly dependent on the deployment of information and communications technology. Customers' insatiable appetite for efficient services has compelled financial institutions to fast track to a more radical transformation of their business systems and models for embracing e-banking. E- Banking appeal as well as its product development is rapidly growing, and the warm acceptance has strongly encouraged its penetration. The success of e-banking is contingent upon reliable and adequate data communication infrastructure. Therefore, it is efficient for banks to invest in online transactions through the creation of networks. However, there has been a mix up between electronic banking and internet banking. The fact is that internet banking is subsumed to electronic banking, and not the other way around (Dawit, 2015).

Banking service provision in just a handful of years has come a long way from the time of ledger cards and other manual filing systems. Most banks today have electronic systems to handle their daily voluminous tasks of information retrieval, storage and processing. Irrespective of whether they are automated or not, banks by their nature are continually involved in all forms of information management on a continuous basis. The computer is of course an

established tool for achieving a competitive edge and optimal resource allocation. Ethiopia with a population size of above 90 million that can all be potentially transformed into banking service subscribers, has a huge potential. With this in mind, the banking service is clearly endowed with excellent growth potential prospects. Electronic banking might be the key to becoming successful in this lucrative and growing sector (Dawit, 2015).

According to Abanawe et al (2013) as a result of increased penetration of electronic banking which has redefined the banking operations in Nigeria and around the world. The study revealed that the adoption of electronic banking has positively and significantly improved the returns on equity (ROE) of Nigerian banks. On the other hand and on the contrary, it also revealed that e-banking has not significantly improved the returns on assets (ROA) of Nigerian banks.

Empirical Literature

Literatures regarding to challenges and prospects of e- payment in Ethiopia is scanty .most of the studies focus on challenges to adopt the e-payment system in Ethiopia. Wondwossen and Tsegai (2005) also studied on the challenges and opportunities of E-payments in Ethiopia; their objective was studying of E-payment practices in developing countries, Africa and Ethiopia. The authors employs interview and on site observation to investigate challenges to E-payment in Ethiopia and found that, the main obstacles to the development of E-payments are, lack of customers trust in the initiatives, Unavailability of payment laws and regulations particularly for E-payment, Lack of skilled manpower and Frequent power disruption. According to Wondwossen and Tsegai (2005), an adequate legal structure and security framework could foster these of E-payments, which is contradicting with the finding of the previous study. Gardachew (2010) conducted research on the opportunities and challenges of E-banking in Ethiopia. The aim of his study was focused on analyzing the status of electronic banking in Ethiopia and investigates the main challenges and opportunities of implementing E-banking system. The author conducted a survey on the existing operating style of banks and identifies some challenges of using E-banking system, such as, lack of suitable legal and regulatory frame works for E-commerce and E- payments, political instability in neighboring countries, high rates of illiteracy and absence of financial networks that links different banks (Gardachew, 2010).

According to Gardachew (2010), Opportunities offered by ICT through e-learning programs and Commitment of the governments on development of ICT infrastructures is considered as drivers of using E-commerce and E-payment systems. Ghazi and Khalid (2012) found that, the most important barriers for E-business growth are technological issues, such as, security risk, quality of internet and cost of implementation to be the most prominent. On the study of Yang (1997), the security of electronic banking “aimed to identify the challenges that oppose electronic banking which are the concerns of security and privacy of information.

The study suggests that solutions to the security issues require the use of software-based systems or hardware- based systems or a hybrid of the two. These software-based solutions involve the use of encryption algorithms, private and public keys, and digital signatures to form software packets known as Secure Electronic Transaction used by MasterCard and Pretty Good Privacy. Hardware-based solutions such as the Smartcard and the Me Chip provide better protection for the confidentiality of personal information. Software-based solutions have the advantage over hardware-based solutions in that they are easy to distribute and are generally less expensive (Balachandher et al, 2010).

According to, Balachandher et al. (2010) have completed a study on the barriers to internet usage on a corporate customer perspective and found that lack of trust on security issue is the main barrier. The study shows that corporate customers only use Internet Banking to a certain extent and feel banks should invest more on security infrastructure and banks should be willing to take full responsibility.

Traditional to modern banking

The introduction of new technologies, then the emergence of a knowledge-based economy and society opportunities of the emergency: Information and communication technology (ICT) advanced this leads Globalization, competition, changing social trends. Paper based payment system to e-payment system unable to respond with manual or paper work- Number of payments increased dramatically (economic transaction) so why banks need to respond it, to maximize their profit (increase capacity of lending), to ensure survival (maintain expected reserves by central bank). The bank responded by providing E-payment product (Card payment, MB, IB...) E-payment as strategic tool for modern banking: Intensified Competition in the

Banking Sector e-payment as Source of Revenue: Offering innovative, premium services to existing customers; attracting new customers by offering innovative services. Adapting to Requirements of Core Target Groups E-payment as Distribution Channel and Image Product (to gain strategic advantages) (CBE, 2023).

ATM Banking Practice in Ethiopia

Certainly, the banking industry in Ethiopia is underdeveloped and therefore there is an immediate need to embark on capacity building arrangements and modernize the banking system by employing the state-of-the-art technology being used anywhere in the world. With a growing number of import-export businesses, and increased international trades and international relations, the current banking system is short of providing efficient and dependable services and therefore all banks operating in Ethiopia should recognize the need for introducing electronic banking system to satisfy their customers and meet the requirements of rapidly expanding domestic and international trades, and increasing international banking services. Undeniably the largest state-owned bank, Commercial Bank of Ethiopia, introduced ATM service for local users in 2001 with its fleet of eight ATMs located in Addis Ababa. Moreover, CBE has had Visa membership since November 14, 2005 (Hanna, 2017).

However, due to lack of appropriate infrastructure it failed to reap the fruit of its membership. Despite, being the pioneer in introducing ATM based payment system and acquired Visa membership. Available services on CBE ATMs are: Cash withdrawal, Balance Inquiry, Mini statement, Fund transfer between accounts attached to a single card and PIN (Personal Identification Number) change. Currently, the bank gives debit service only for Visa cards. CBE clients can withdraw up to 10,000 birr in cash and can buy goods and services of up to 100,000 birr per day. Expanding its leadership, CBE has begun accepting MasterCard in addition to Visa credit cards it began serving over four years ago. The first ever electronic banking gateway was signed between Ethiopian Commodity Exchange (ECX) and CBE. The electronic banking system being developed with CBE is designed to give a secure electronic data sharing gateway between clients, banks and ECX, facilitating a smooth transaction (Hanna, 2017).

The Relationship between Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

The status or prestige of an organization is determined by the quality of the provided services. Organization of high quality level of its services has a high competitive position achieving a high level of service meet the needs of customers. Studies confirmed that service quality and customer satisfaction have strong relationship (Alagheband, 2006; Bedi, 2011; Keingham, 2005). When the customer receives high quality service is behavior and attitude towards the organization will be positive and that would strengthen the relationship with the organization and vice versa. Customer satisfaction is the most important criteria that enable organization to ensure the quality of their goods or services (Sintayehu, 2015).

In case of the banking sector, recognized standard scales to measure the perceived quality of a bank service is not available. Thus providing high quality service is being taken as an important weapon to survive and to gain and maintain competitive advantage (Bateson, 1985) cited in Thaakur (2011). For commodity like products, quality can be measured easily by its features. But quality of service depends heavily on the quality of the personnel of service provider or the provider himself. Studies on customers' switching from banks have found that they considered to be poorly serviced. Quality service improved customer satisfaction and reduced customer erosion (Thakur, 2011). Service quality is the key to measure e-banking user satisfaction. Researchers have paid much attention to the close relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction (Sintayehu, 2015).

Conceptual framework

Figure 1: Dependencies in delivery of service through the ATM

Research Methodology

Research Area Description

This study was focused on challenges and opportunities of ATM and POS banking on Dukem area CBE branches namely Dukem Branch, Oda Nebe Branch, Kurkura Branch, Alibira and Tedecha branch.

Research Design

The study descriptive study design used mixed approach (quantitative and qualitative method) to analyze for data collected from customers. The reason behind using descriptive study design is because the researcher is interested in describing the existing situation under study. This study used descriptive analysis that to describes the challenges and opportunities of ATM and POS banking.

Population of the Study

There are about 15,416 ATM and POS Machine users in this area. Out of these total users, 9,949 are active users of the ATMs and POSs Machine. Simple random sampling method used customers and the employees of the bank to select from the determined sample.

Sample Design

For the purpose of this study, the researcher used probability sampling design. There are five (5) branches which are in Dukem area which will be included in the sample. Researchers have decided to take some selected branches to get adequate data by considering the total numbers of ATM users in the Dukem area.

Sample Size

The target population of this study focused on the ATM and POS machine users CBE Dukem area. The total population target sizes are 15,416 users of the CBE Dukem area branches. Out of this 9,949 are active ATM users the remaining 4,374 are inactive ATM users and the rest 1,093 cards are under process of the bank. The sampling frame is the list of all elements from which the sample is drawn. For this research, the sampling frame is list of CBE in Dukem area

The researcher's customer's formula to calculate the minimum size out of 9,949 targeted active ATM users in the Dukem area. Yemane's formula found the following formula to determine the

sample size which is trustworthy when the population size is known. By considering the homogeneity of the respondents and to reduce the sample size the researchers applied 7% precision level in the formula.

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

$$1+N(e)^2$$

n = Sample Size N =

Total Population e =

Error Term

$$n = \frac{9,949.00}{1+9,949(0.07)^2} = \frac{9,949.00}{1+9,949(0.0049)} = 199.97 \sim 200$$

$$\frac{9,949.00}{1+9,949(0.07)^2} \quad \frac{9,949.00}{1+9,949(0.0049)}$$

Data Source and method of data collection

The data used for the study to be collecting from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data was collected through questionnaires filled by customers of ATMs and POSs machine users and employees of the bank. The secondary data was collected from relevant documents, organization reports. When necessary, material was downloaded from most referred web sites and the Website of the Bank.

Data Processing and Analysis

Data used manually extracted by key common issues, coded and analyzed by categorization, classification and summarization techniques using SPSS Version 22. The data was analyzed through descriptive statistics such as mean, table, frequency and percentage as appropriate. The findings will be systematically organized, summarized and presented in the form of figures and tables as appropriate.

Validity and Reliability

Validity test

Harper and Thompson (2011) note that in order for data collection tools to provide useful results, the questions must be both valid and reliable. According to Creswell (2009), the usual procedure in assessing the content validity of a measure is to use a professional or expert in a particular field which helps in discovering question content, correction in the wording and the sequencing problems before the actual study as well as exploring ways of improving overall quality of study. For the sake of this study, the researcher will use the opinions of experts in the field of study especially highly officials from commercial banks to establish the validity of the research instrument. Also the researcher also used opinions of experts of the organization for the questionnaires whether they are correctly processed or not. This will facilitate the necessary revision and modification of the research instrument thereby enhancing validity.

Reliability

Reliability of the data collection instrument is the consistency of measurement and frequently assessed using a test–retest reliability method (Cooper and Schinder, 2014). Reliability enables the researcher to identify the ambiguities and inadequate items in the research instrument; where the instrument reliability is the dependability, consistency or trustworthiness of a test. The scores were tested using Cronbach’s Alpha for the data to be reliable for those questionnaires raised by likert scale. According to George & Mallery (2003), it is recommended that if a Cronbach’s coefficient of measurement scale exceeds 0.70 is acceptable as an internally consistent so that further analysis can be carried unless it is unacceptable.

George and Mallery indicated the Cronbach alpha in the following rule of thumb concerning reliability coefficient: If alpha is greater than 0.9 it gives excellent result, if the result of the alpha is from 0.8 up to 0.9 it results in good study, If the alpha is between 0.7 to 0.8 the result generated will be acceptable, alpha result less than 0.7 but greater than 0.6

is questionable, if the alpha goes between 0.5 to 0.6 the result found is considered to be poor and when alpha is less than 0.5 the result is unacceptable.

Category of questionnaire or Scale	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
Opportunities of e-banking factor	0.723	6
Challenges of e-banking factor	0.720	4
Customer Service	0.710	8
Total	0.788	18

Result and Analysis

Descriptive Analysis

Types of account

From the result of the sample respondents 86.1% of 155 respondents were users of saving accounts and the rest 13.9% of 25 were users of current account users and all most majority of the users are ordinary saving account holders

The year of the customers of the bank

The result that from the total respondents of 2.2% of 4 are have been the customers of the bank 1year or less than 13.9 of 25 respondents are 1year up to 3years 32.8% of 59 respondents are 4years up to 5years 22.8% of 41 respondents are 6years up to 8years and the rest 28.3% of 51 the respondents are above 8years customers of the bank. So this indicates that the majority of the CBE customers are 4 up 5years and above that the customers of the bank.

Electronic banking service and frequency of visits the bank

The respondent for e-banking service delivery channel 95% of 171 the total respondents Uses ATM and POS the rest 5% of 9 respondents“ uses ATM and POS. Even though, those responded the questioner fill during visiting the ATM and POS that is why mobile banking and internet banking have not responded by users. Describing those visit the branch and using ATM and POS for transact their accounts usually 63.3%of 114 before the introduction of e-banking service but those respondents who visits the branch sometimes 33.9% of 61 account only and the remaining 2.8% of 5 are a card holder but they didn't visit ATM and POS machine.

The customer satisfaction of ATM and POS banking service

The result describe the no of year have been using ATM and POS banking service from the total respondents 14.4% of the 26 are said that 1years or less than 30.6% of the 55 respondents are said between 1years up to 3years 34.4% of the 62 respondents are said between 4years up to 6years and the remaining 20.6% of the 37 respondents are have been 5years and above. The majority of the customer of commercial bank of Ethiopia are use ATM and POS banking 4years and above.

Satisfaction of after using ATM and POS service: The response of customers question which compare the satisfaction of customer between ordinary banking and e-banking 86.1% of the 155 respondents said that e-banking has given them more satisfaction than ordinary banking and only 13.9% of the 25 said they are dissatisfied.

Distance/location/ and understanding of ATM and POS

The result show that the number of respondents 30.6% of 55 are strongly agree they have got by the reasonable distance of ATM and POS machine, 36.1% of 65 number of respondents are agreed on the place of the ATM and POS machine avail 23.9% of 43 are neutral 7.2% of 13 are disagree and only 2.2% of 4 are strongly disagree. From this it indicates that from the Dukem area the five branches are built on the flow of main road that's why most of respondents are agreed the location of CBEs ATM and POS machine.

From the total respondents of ATM and POS users 38.9% of 70 are strongly agree on the understanding of ATM and POS machine 48.9% of 88 are agreed 8.3% of 15 are said neutral and the remaining 3.9% of 7 of respondents are disagree. Unfortunately, those respondents are their academically background is from diploma and above and also most of them are so young. Because of this, reason the interference of simple and easy to understand the ATM and POS machine.

In the same table result show that 30.9% of 54 from the total respondents are strongly agree on the location of ATM and POS machines are safe to withdraw money 40% of 72 of the respondents are agreed 18.3% of 33 respondents are said neutral 10% of 18 respondents are disagreed and the rest of 1.7% of 3 respondents are strongly disagree. From this point of view 40% of 72 from the total respondents are agreed this indicates that the five branches of CBE in Dukem area the ATM and POS machines are available near to the branch covered by temporary shade in a secured manner.

The service of ATM and POS banking

The respondent result shows that numbers of 2.2% of 4 respondents are said strongly agree on the service of ATM and POS banking 24hr/7days a week provide by CBE. And 11.7% of 21 respondents are said agree 33.3% of 60 respondents are said neutral 36.1% of 65 number of respondents are said disagree and 6.7% of 30 number of respondents are said strongly disagree. The esteem questioners fill those responses are the majority of disagreed by the service they get from CBEs ATM and POS 24/7 days. The reason why the respondents are disagreeing the poor network, power supply interruption during the machine is processed and by others.

The level of satisfaction for this question the number of 25% of 45 respondents are strongly agree and 42.8% of 77 respondents are agree 23.9% of 43 respondents are neutral and the remaining 8.3% of 15 of respondents are disagree. In sum up, the respondents of the above getting from ATM and POS banking service is higher than ordinary banking service most of them are they agreed on they can get the service at any time includes holiday and off days when they want to withdraw money and it reduced a waiting time on the branches but the ordinary banking having a time limit. The customers must appear physically withdraw cash.

The same table indicate that the number of 7.8% of 14 respondents are strongly agree on ATM and POS banking can do as employees do and also 26.7% of 48 respondents are agree 21.7% of 39 respondents are neutral 43.2% of 78 respondents are disagree and only 0.6 of 1 are said strongly disagree. The majority of esteem customers 43.2% of 78 are disagree. Because of this the researcher observed during processed of the ATM and POS the system is fail when they are use it might be the fear is come from this point of view.

Opportunities and challenges of expansion ATM and POS banking

Results reported on the above issue, shows that 0.6% of 1 response strongly agree 22.2% of 40 respondents are agreed 32.2% of 58 respondents are neutral and 40.6% of 73 respondents are said disagreed and the remaining 4.4% of 8 respondents are strongly disagreed. The largest number of respondents 40.6% or 73 out of the total respondents were disagreed that the appropriate of technological infrastructure to support the service. Similarly, the study of Wondwossen and Tsegai (2005) stated that lack of sufficient telecommunication infrastructure is one of the basic challenges in the development of E-payment in Ethiopia.

As it is depicted on the above table, respondents were asked whether, the opportunities for expansion of ATM and POS banking service in the city the large numbers of 45% of 85 respondents are agreed. It indicates that in Dukem area there is a chance to expansion of ATMs and POSs machine in the city. And the customers of CBE in Dukem Area need more ATMs and POSs machine around this area.

In the same table from the total respondents 19.4% of 35 are strongly agreed on the challenges of ATM and POS banking expansion on the city and the number of 27.8% of 50 respondents are agreed 26.7% of 48 are neutral 14.4% of 26 disagreed and the rest 11.7% of 21 of respondents are strongly disagree. This result show that the majority of respondents are agreed on the challenges of expansion ATMs and POSs on the city as it mention on the above lack of infrastructure and lack of telecommunication and other reasons.

Overall service quality and customer satisfaction

As can be seen from the results of the survey presented on the above issue, 10.5% of 19 respondents are said excellent on their saving habit after starting uses ATM and POS machine

16.7% of 30 respondents are said very good 22.2% of 40 respondents are said good and 43.2% of 78 respondents are said poor the rest 7.4% of 13 respondents are said extremely poor. From this it can observe most of the respondents are their saving habit is poor after them starting to use ATM and POS banking service.

The number of respondents gave to answer 29.4% of the 53 respondents are said excellent the overall service quality of ATM and POS service 47.2% of 85 respondents are said very good 20.0% of 36 respondents are said good and the rest only 3.3% of 6 respondents are said poor. This indicates the majority of the commercial bank of Ethiopia customers are satisfied on the service quality of ATM and POS delivered by CBE.

And from the total numbers of respondents 37.2% of 67 are very satisfied 48.3% of 81 customers are satisfied 11.7% of the 21 customers are neutral 2.2% of the 4 respondents are dissatisfied and the remaining 0.6% of the 1 respondent is highly dissatisfied. From the above table 12 observe the majority of the users of ATM and POS to transact and from the overall feedback they got from customer the technology has given more satisfaction to customers.

Inferential Analysis

Regression assumptions

Before joining regression analysis, it is essential to test assumptions of multiple linear regression analysis Model (Keith, 2006; Pallant, 2005). Therefore, each assumption result was discussed below:

Normality test

Another important diagnostics test conducted in this study is the normality assumption (i.e. the normally distributed errors). The normality assumption is about the mean of the residuals is zero. Moreover, Normality tests are used to determine whether a data set is well-modeled by a normal distribution or not, or to compute how likely an underlying random variable is to be normally distributed (Gujarati, 2009). Therefore, the researcher used histogram for testing the normality of the data.

According to Fidell (2001), if the residuals are normally distributed around its mean of zero, the histogram should be a bell-shaped and regression standardized residual plotted between 3.3 and -3.3 . So that, from table 4.10 below, it can be noted that the data conforms to the normality assumption (Stevens, 2009). As we can understand from the histogram and p-p plot depicted below, the residuals seem normally distributed and the residuals are distributed with a mean of 0 and standard deviation of 0.990 which is approximately 1. Thus, the model fulfills the assumption of being normally distributed. Moreover, in the normal probability plot it is expected that our points will lie in a reasonably straight diagonal line from bottom left to top right which would suggest no major deviations from normality.

Residuals Statistics

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	1.6671	3.6828	2.8469	.46488	180
Residual	-.82338	1.19568	.00000	.43270	180
Std. Predicted Value	-2.538	1.798	.000	1.000	180
Std. Residual	-1.883	2.734	.000	.990	180

Source: Own survey data, 2023

Linearity test

This is slightly different from simple linear regression as we have multiple explanatory variables. Multiple regressions can accurately estimate the relationship between dependent and independent variables, when their relationship is linear in nature (Keith, 2006). If linearity is violated, all the estimates of the regression including regression coefficients, standard errors, and tests of statistical significance may be biased (Keith, 2006). This can be best checked by p-p plot residual as shown in the appendixes. When, p-p residual looks at straight line, the relationship between the dependent and independent variables is linear.

Therefore, there is no linearity problem on the data used for this study.

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Source: Own data survey, 2023

Autocorrelation test

For any two observations the residual terms should be uncorrelated (or independent). This eventuality is sometimes described as a lack of autocorrelation. The researcher used and tested this with the Durbin–Watson (DW) test, which tests for serial correlations among errors. A value substantially below 2 (and especially a value less than 1) means that the data is positively auto correlated, i.e. on average a data element is close to the subsequent data element. A value of d substantially above 2 means that the data is negatively auto correlated, i.e. on average a data element is far from the subsequent data element. Thus, the DW test from the appendix shows Sig. F Change 1.805 which means the data is positively

auto correlated. This implies that there is no problem with the assumption of autocorrelation and the variables are good predictors of E-Banking.

Table : Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.732 ^a	.536	.526	.43728	1.805

Source: own data survey, 2023

Heteroscedasticity test

Heteroscedasticity statistics checked is used to measure model fitness. The variance of the residuals for every set of values for the independent variable should be equal and violation is called Heteroscedasticity. This means that investigators assume that errors are spread out consistently between the balanced score card. Scatter plot of more than 3.3 or less than -3.3 indicates a Heteroscedasticity problem (Tabachnick&Fidell, 2007). Therefore, as shown in appendix the data did not violate Heteroscedasticity assumption and instead it was homoscedastic.

Source: Own data survey, 2023

Correlation Analysis

Correlation is a statistical tool to determine the strength of relationship between two suitability variables. Therefore, correlation matrix is an interpretation of the correlations is based on a significant of the correlation between two or more variables. The ranges of r value from -1 to +1, which used to describe a direction relationship between two variables. Among them, minus means the relationship between two variables is negative, and if the greater the absolute value of correlation coefficient, the stronger the relationship. It shows that if one variable becomes bigger and another variable will become to smaller. For plus sign means a positive relationship between two variables, a variable tends to directly become bigger with another variable, or smaller and smaller with this variable (direct relation). When correlation coefficient equal to 0, it means the weakest relationship between two variables. The correlation matrix table is a comparison of needs, requirements, or functions whereby the user identifies a relationship of either mutual benefit, conflict, or no.

Table : Correlations

		ATM	POS
ATM	Pearson Correlation	1	.579**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
POS	Pearson Correlation	.579**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Model Summary

The table below gives the regression model summary results. It presents the R value which is the measure of association between the dependent and the independent variables, the R Square which is the coefficient of determination measuring the extent at which the independent variables influence the dependent variable as well as the Adjusted R Square which measures the reliability of the regression results.

Table : Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.732 ^a	.536	.526	.43728	1.805

So, a value of 0.732 offers good or significant level of prediction (Creswell 2012). The predictive capacity is the square of the correlation coefficient and it is 0.536 (R square or R²) for this model.

Therefore, the researcher can conclude that in this study 53.6% of the variation of E-banking is explained by the variation in the independent variables. The regression model is modest in terms of goodness fit since the R square value is 0.536 which is/has moderate effect according to Muijis guideline quoted by Cohen, et al., (2007).

Significance Level (ANOVA)

Analysis of the variance (ANOVA) was used to make simultaneous comparisons between means; thus, testing whether a significant relation exists between dependent and independent variables. ANOVA indicates a significant F statistic implying that the model was fit for the estimation.

The results presented in table 4.14 gives the ANOVA results which shows the reliability of the model developed in explaining the relationship between the study variables. The significance of the model was tested at 5% level with a 2-tailed test.

Table : ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	31.120	3	10.373	54.252	.000 ^b
1 Residual	26.961	177	.191		
Total	58.081	180			

From the table above, the F statistic is 54.252 with a distribution F (3,141), and the probability of observing a value greater than or equal to 54.252 is less than 0.001 as given by the significance value of 0.000 which is less than the critical value at 5% level in a 2-tailed test. This therefore, reveals that the regression model developed is statistically significant and

the variation in the results is insignificant that cannot result to a much difference in case of a change in the study units (population).

The ANOVA table shown above result indicates that the overall model is significant. The analysis of variance shows significant relationship between dimensions the independent variables and E-banking because the ANOVA value 0.000 is smaller than P value (0.05) which indicates the level of statistical significance. Hence, we can conclude that the overall linear regression model is significant.

Conclusion

Whereas the study focused on challenges and Opportunities of ATM and POS banking in the case of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia in Dukem Area. The study as discussed based on the field survey of 2023, has come up with major findings regarding the challenges and opportunities of ATM and POS banking in case of CBE. Analyzed the findings in terms of their magnitude and possible implication in different aspects, based on the major findings the following conclusions are drawn.

- Most of the respondents are agreed on the location of ATM and POS machine because the five branches of Dukem area ATMs are built on the flow of main road and the majority of respondents are agreed on that CBEs ATMs and POSs are safe to withdraw money.
- The tremendous number of respondents are a long-time customer of commercial bank of Ethiopia in Dukem area, it also has a positive impact on the bank.
- Most of the parameters which measures benefit of ATM and POS banking were rated as “agreed”. It implied that customers get benefits by using ATM and POS banking. However, as the finding of the study disclosed the majority of the respondents agreed on that were attracted by ATM and POS banking service due to its cash availability, easiness and accessibility.
- Frequent power interruption: Lack of reliable power supply is a key challenge for smoothly running e-banking in study area and almost all of the respondents agreed that CBE ATM and POS banking services are affected by Ethio-telecom network

infrastructure. It leads to conclusion that improves ATM and POS banking system, there is a need to do more with Ethio-telecom.

- The majority of respondents are using ATM the few of the respondents were using POS terminals, It is concluded that they need awareness to transact using POS terminals including CBE branches, hotels, super market, pharmacy and other place which is found CBEs POS machine in Dukem area.
- Resistance to changes in technology among customers and staff due to: Lack of awareness on the benefits of new technologies, Fear of risk, Lack of trained personnel in key organizations, Tendency to be content with the existing structures, People are found resistant to new payment mechanisms.
- The largest number of respondents was disagreed on that the appropriate of technological infrastructure to support the service, and the respondents are need that the expansion of ATMs and POSs machine in the city.
- Most of the respondents are “agreed”, on they can checked the remaining amount immediately on the spot of the machine after they used ATM and POS machine, this also have a positive impact to the bank.
- High cost of Internet or Absence of financial networks that links different banks (Banks are not yet automated): Most of the banking-transactions currently taking place use credit and debit cards supplied by Visa and MasterCard.
- Generally, lack of suitable legal and regulatory framework for e-commerce and e-payment: Ethiopian current laws do not accommodate electronic contracts and signatures. Ethiopia has not yet enacted legislation that deals with e-commerce concerns including enforceability of the validity of electronic contracts, digital signatures and restrict the use of encryption technologies.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study the following possible recommendations were forwarded:

- The bank should be communicated with telecommunication and make ready generator when the power if off in order to minimize the network failure.

- The bank should be focus on the technology especially telecommunication because it is very important to e-payment in Ethiopia generally and the study are specifically.
- The tremendous number of responses from the total number of respondents are disagreed on the service of the CBE provided promptly delivered ATM card. To avoid these banks should be giving attention on the delivery cards promptly that means minimizing the time between application and delivery actual cards to the customers.
- In order to solve the problem of language, the banks should follow multi language as much as possible.
- The banks should give due to provide training for their employees regarding the e-payments process, system and procedures. Unless otherwise the service provided by the bank or branch is not quality service.
- To avoid the failures of completing transaction as per request of the customer they should timely follow up the ATM and POS machine and make adjustment easily.

Reference

1. (Million Asefa, 2013). The impact of electronic banking on customers" satisfaction in Ethiopia banking industry (the case of customers of Dashen and Wogagen banks in Gonder city)
2. (Michael Adbibo, 2013). Challenges and opportunities of electronic banking: a case Dashen bank and nib international bank
3. (CBE E-payment Procedure V.1). Part 1 (ATM, POS and card) part 2 (Mobile and Internet Banking) version 1.0 Sep, 2012.
4. (CBE E-payment training, 2023). CBE E-payment training overview 2007
5. (Mohammad, 2012). Challenge and prospect of E-banking in Ethiopia
6. Megersa, N. (2010). The Role and Performance of International Banking In Financing International Trade. Addis Ababa. Mimeo
7. Jornal of Business Management & Social Sciences Research (JBM&SSR) ISSN No: 22012958 Volume 5 May 2015 ATM Adoption of Customers in Commercial Bank of Ethiopia (CBE). Mekelle
8. Shah, M., and Clarke, S. (2009). E-Banking Management: Issues, Solution, and Strategies, Information Science Reference, Hershey, New York.
9. Ovia, J. (2002). Payment System and Financial Innovations, A paper presented at the Annual Policy Conference, Nov. 2002.

10. Chavan, J. (2013). Internet banking benefits and challenges in an emerging economy, *International Journal of Research in Business Management (IJRBM)*, 1(1), 19-26.
11. Elisha Menson (2010). E-banking in developing economy: empirical evidence from Nigeria, *journal of applied quantitative methods*, 5(2).
12. Edojariogba, P. (2014). *Electronic Banking Channels and Customers' Preferences*, A Research Dissertation Submitted to the Department of Business Administration University of Benin, Nigeria.
13. Edemivwaye (2015). *Electronic Banking and Customer Satisfaction in the Nigerian Banking Sector*, *The International Journal Of Humanities & Social Studies (ISSN 2321 - 9203)*.
14. Okechi, O., and Oruan, M.K. (2013). Empirical Evaluation of Customers' Use of Electronic Banking Systems in Nigeria, *African Journal of Computing and ICT*, Volume 6, No.1.
15. Fumiko, etal (2003). *A Guide to the ATM and Debit Card Industry*", Payments System Research Department Federal Reserve Bank of Kansas City Kansas City, Missouri,USA.
16. (D.W.Faulkner, Alan Harmer-1998). *ATM and Multimedia networks* page 71 (David Ginsburg-1999), *Implementing ADSL* page 159).
17. (Abor,J.(2004). *Technological innovation and banking in Ghana: An evaluation of Customers perception*, American Academy of Financial Management.
18. (Sherif, 2006). *Electronic banking & e-readiness adoption by CommercialBanks in Pakistan*.
19. Dawit Tesfaye, (2015). *Opportunities and Challenges of Electronic Banking Service*
20. *Rendering the case of Commercial Bank of Ethiopia*
21. Abaenewe, Z.C., Ogbulu, O.M. and Ndugbu, O. (2013). *Electronic Banking and Bank Performance in Nigeria*, *West African Journal of Industrial & Academic Research*, 6(1).
22. Wondwossen Tadesse and Tsegai G.kidane, (2005). *E-payment: Challenge and Opportunity in Ethiopia*
23. Gardachew Worku, (2010). *Electronic Banking in Ethiopia - Practice, Opportunities and Challenges*. Addis Abeba, Ethiopia. Retrieved from [Http://: Ssrn.com/abstract +14920066](Http://Ssrn.com/abstract+14920066)
24. Yang, Y. (1997). *The security of Electronic Banking a research Paper presented at this nation formation systems security Conference Vol.6 PP.PP 505 – 525. USA*
25. (Hanna Andargacbew, 2017). *Assessing the ATM Service Quality of CBE in Adis Abeba*
26. Balachandher, K.G, Santha V.Norazlin, I.and Prasad,R.(2010). *Electronic banking in Malaysia: a note on evolution of services and consumer reactions*. *Journal of Internet Banking and Commence*. Vol 5, no.15.
27. (Endalkachew Abebe, 2013). *Assessing the Impact of Core Banking and Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction in Commercial Bank of Ethiopia (A case of Bishoftu Branch)*

28. (Parasuraman, A, Zeithml, V. & Berry, L. (1985). A Conceptual Model of Service Quality & its Implications for Future Research. Journal of Marketing, Vol. 49.
29. (Omari. Richard Kwaku Bamfo, 2012). An assessment of the use of ATM of Barclays bank Gahana Limited akim oda branch (PG4134210 Sep 2012) (Alagheband, 2006; Bedi, 2011; Keingham, 2005).
30. (Sintayehu Yitbarek, 2015). The Impacts of E - banking Services on Customer Satisfaction: the case of selected commercial banks in Addis Ababa
31. Thakur, S (2011). Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty. A study with special reference to India Banking Industries. The journal of Sri Krishna research and Educational Consortium Vol. 1(5), PP. 83 - 93.
32. Ngechu M (2003) Understanding the Research Process and Methods - An Introduction, University of Nairobi. 1st Edition
33. Ghazi and Khalid (2012) Challenges and Prospects of Payment Card In Dashen Bank Share Company in Addis Ababa (CBE Public Web) [www.http/cbe](http://cbe) web. Cite